

[conjecture]

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Time is a discrete dynamical system

Open Mathematics Collaboration*[†]

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Abstract

We conjecture that quantum vacuum operates its discrete dynamics in a superposition of a class of iterating functions such that each physical system operates within a distinct function.

keywords: discrete dynamical system, quantum time, conjecture

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
<https://osf.io/8f4yg/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4815259>

Introduction

1. This white paper is related to [1].
2. More about dynamical systems, chaos, and fractals can be found in [2–8].

Conjecture

3. $\text{time} := \textit{sequence of iterations of a discrete dynamical system}$
4. Each iteration of (3) corresponds to one tick of the clock.

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Class of functions

5. Regarding (3), we define the following.
6. Let \mathcal{T} be a class of functions and $t_i \in \mathcal{T}$ with $i \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.
7. $t_i : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$
8. $t_i(z) \in \mathbb{C}$, $z = x + iy$
9. $x = \text{Re}(t_i(z))$ is the space dimension.

Quantum vacuum

10. The idea of (3) is to describe physical processes in terms of (6)–(9).

Brainstorming

11. Fractal dimension simulates extra dimensions.
12. For example, the fractal dimension of the Mandelbrot set has 2 dimensions, meaning, one needs two dimensions to cover its boundary [2].

Final Remarks

13. We propose that **time** is a mathematical operation in space; *each iteration of the discrete dynamical system $t(z)$ results in one tick of the clock.*
14. Dynamical systems produce fractals.
15. The fractal nature present in our observable universe in both macro and micro scales reinforces (3) and [1].

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [9, 10].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to `mplobo@uft.edu.br`.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [11, 12].

How to cite this paper?

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Agreement

All authors agree with [10].

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